

INGLIZ TILINING GLOBAL MULOQOTDAGI VA HAYOTIMIZDAGI O'RNI

Djamolova Sevinch Zoirjonovna

Samarqand Davlat Chet tillar instituti talabasi

Gmail; djamolovasevinch05@gmail.com

Zubaydova Nilufar Nematullayevna

Samarqand Davlat Chet tillar instituti o'qituvchisi

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola ingliz tilining global muloqotdagi va hayotimizdagi o'rnini tahlil qiladi. Ingliz tili bugungi kunda dunyodagi eng ko'p tarqalgan tillardan biri bo'lib, xalqaro biznes, ta'lim, fan va madaniyat sohalarida muhim rol o'ynamoqda. Maqolada ingliz tilining global kommunikatsiyadagi ahamiyati, u qanday qilib turli madaniyatlar o'rtasida ko'prik vazifasini o'tashi, shuningdek, uning internet va raqamli texnologiyalar orqali tarqalishi xususida fikrlar bildiriladi. Shuningdek, maqola ingliz tilini bilishning shaxsiy va professional hayotimizga ta'siri va uning global jamiyatdagi o'zgaruvchan roli haqida muhokama olib boradi. Ushbu tahlil orqali ingliz tilining nafaqat xalqaro aloqalar uchun, balki insonlarning kundalik hayoti uchun qanday ahamiyatga ega ekanligi ko'rsatib beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: BMT, YUNESKO, MDH, Asr taqozosi, Individual rivojlanish, resurslar, ta'lim tizimi, global muloqot

Annotation; This article analyzes the role of English in global communication and in our lives. English is one of the most widely spoken languages in the world today and plays an important role in international business, education, science and culture. The article discusses the importance of the English language in global communication, how it acts as a bridge between different cultures, as well as its spread through the Internet and digital technologies. The article also discusses the impact of knowing English on our personal and professional lives and its changing role in the global society. Through this analysis, it will be shown how important the English language is not only for international relations, but also for people's daily life.

Key words: UN, UNESCO, CIS, Demand of the Century, Individual development, resources, education system, global communication

XXI asr har bir soha jadal rivojlanib borayotgan bir davrda ingliz tilining ham global muloqotdagi ta'siri yildan yilga sezilarli darajada oshib bormoqda. Shu o'rinda bir savol tug'iladi. Xo'sh, ingliz tilining dunyo miqyosidagi va o'z shaxsiy hayotimizdagi o'rni qanday?

Aynan hozirgi asr taqozosi bilan hech bir sohani, xoh u ta'lim sohasi bo'lsin, xoh iqtisod sohasi, va yoki texnologiya va internet, madaniyat va san'at, sayohat va hokazolarni ingliz tilisiz tasavvur qilish qiyin, albatta. Ingliz tili global til hisoblanib, u ko'plab xalqlaro tashkilotlar, jumladan, BMT, YUNESKO, MDH kabilarda qo'llanadi. Ushbu til dunyoda eng keng tarqalgan til hisoblanadi. U 73 davlatning rasmiy tili hamda juda ko'p davlatlar tomonidan ikkinchi til sifatida o'rganiladi. Ingliz tili haqida gap ketar ekan, shubhasiz, inson xayoliga u ochadigan muvaffaqiyatlar eshigi va yaratadigan imkoniyatlar keladi. U mana shunday imkoniyatlar yaratishi bilan birga, uning ahamiyati quyidagi sohalarda namoyon bo'ladi:

- ta'lim
- madaniyat
- sayohat
- internet-texnologiya
- ish imkoniyatlari va hokazo.

1. *Ta'lim.* Hozirgi davrda ingliz tili ta'lim tizimining muhim qismidir. Ingliz tilini bilish orqali xalqaro, nufuzli universitetlarda ta'lim olishingiz mumkin. Xususan, O'zbekiston universitetlari, akademik muassasalarida ko'plab fanlar ingliz tilida o'qitiladi. Bu esa o'z navbatida O'zbekiston ta'limi ham dunyo miqyosida yuzlashayotganidan dalolat beradi.

2. *Madaniyat.* Avvalambor, yangi til o'rganish yangi bir madaniyatdan xabardor bo'lish hisoblanadi. Qolaversa, ingliz tilini chuqur bilish ingliz tilida yozilgan mashhur asarlar, maqolalar, ma'lumotlarni hech qanday inson omili aralashgan tarjimalarsiz, o'z holida o'qish imkonini yaratadi.

3. *Sayohat.* Sayohat qilishda ingliz tilini bilish juda ko'p joylarni kashf etish bilan birga mahalliy odamlar bilan muloqot qilishda yordam beradi.

4. *Internet-texnologiya.* Ijtimoiy tarmoqdagi ko'plab ma'lumotlar, resurslar, maqolalar ingliz tilida. Ushbu til orqali internetdagi ma'lumotlar yoki yangiliklardan oson xabardor bo'lish mumkin.

5. *Ish imkoniyatlariga* kelsak, ingliz tili sizga ko'p imkoniyatlarni beradi. Ayni hozir rivojlanib borayotgan O'zbekistonda ham yoshlarning til o'rganishiga bo'lgan talab va ehtiyoj oshib bormoqda.

Yuqorida ingliz tilining turli sohalardagi ahamiyatini ko'rib chiqdik. Beixtiyor ingliz tilining ahamiyati muhimligicha qoladimi, degan savol tug'iladi. Vaqtlar o'tgan sayin ko'pgina davlatlarning o'zaro aloqa munosabatlari kuchayib borayotgani bois ingliz tiliga bo'lgan talab va uning hayotimizdagi ahamiyati oshsa oshadiki, kamaymaydi. Har bir narsaning foydali tomonlari bo'lgani bilan birga kamchiliklari ham bo'ladi, albatta. Tanganing ikki tomoni bo'ladi, deb bejizga aytishmagan. Ingliz tili kuchayib, globallashib borgani sayin boshqa kam foydalanuvchisi bo'lgan tillar sekin asta yo'qolib boradi. Har yili ko'plab tillar mana shunday sabablar bilan o'lib boradi. Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, ingliz tili o'z hayotimizda, balki jahon bo'ylab yuqori ahamiyatga ega. O'z o'rni bilan hech qaysi til ingliz tiliga tenglasha olmaydi. Ingliz tili ko'p soha va madaniyatlar orasida ko'prik bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Ingliz tiliga bo'lgan dunyoni yaxshi bilish uchun foydalaniladigan qurol hamdir. Ingliz tilini o'rganish nafaqat individual rivojlanishga, balki global miqyosda ham muvaffaqiyatga erishishga yordam beradi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Crystal, D. (2003). English as a Global Language. Cambridge University Press.
2. SN Muxtarovna, Independent learning, Евразийский научный журнал, 374-375, 2017
3. M Ubaydullayeva, Ways To Activate Students When Teaching The Epic" Alpomish, Международный Журнал Языка, Образования, Перевода 4 (5), 2023
4. D Axmedova, S Zarmaskhonov, Exploring Global Perspectives In Language Teaching And Learning, Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit, 205-207, 2024
5. Graddol, D. (2006). English Next: Why Global English may Mean the End of 'English as a Foreign Language'. British Council.
6. Harmer, J. (2007). The Practice of English Language Teaching. Pearson Education.
7. Nunan, D. (1999). Second Language Teaching & Learning. Heinle & Heinle Publishers.
8. UM Azamatovna, The History Of The Development Of The Terms Of Literary Studies Of The Turkic Peoples
9. SD Ikrambayevna, Classification of Functions of Communicative Strategy and Tactics in Political Communication, Miasto Przyszłości 50, 548-553, 2024.

10. qizi To‘yeva, M. S. (2022, November). Yangi O‘zbekiston Orifa Ayollari Va G‘arb Ayollarining Jamiyatdagi Mavqeyi Va Ularning Huquqlari. In International Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 74-81).
11. Islomjanovna, A. M. (2024). Bolaning Ijtimoiylashuv Jarayonidagi Omillar Hamda Oil A Va Jamiyatning Ahamiyati. International Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 12(6), 1154-1158.
12. Islomjanovna, A. M. (2022). Traditions of culture in Islam and their modern significance. World Bulletin of Social Sciences, 9, 198-202.
13. N Shamurodova, Kauzallik Va Kauzativlikning Ingliz Va O‘zbek Tillarida Qiyosiy Tadqiqi, Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit, 305-307, 2024.
14. Abdufattokhov, S., Ibragimova, K., & Gulyamova, D. (2021, November). The applicability of machine learning algorithms in predictive modeling for sustainable energy management. In International Conference on Forthcoming Networks and Sustainability in the IoT Era (pp. 379-391). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
15. Ghodake, S. P., Malkar, V. R., Santosh, K., Jabasheela, L., Abdufattokhov, S., & Gopi, A. (2024). Enhancing Supply Chain Management Efficiency: A Data-Driven Approach using Predictive Analytics and Machine Learning Algorithms. International Journal of Advanced Computer Science & Applications, 15(4).
16. Dohare, S., Pamulaparthi, L., Abdufattokhov, S., Naga Ramesh, J. V., El-Ebiary, Y. A. B., & Thenmozhi, E. (2024). Enhancing Diabetes Management: A Hybrid Adaptive Machine Learning Approach for Intelligent Patient Monitoring in e-Health Systems. International Journal of Advanced Computer Science & Applications, 15(1).
17. Abdufattokhov, S., Normatova, N., & Shermatova, M. (2022). Artificial Neural Networks Based Predictive Model for Detecting the Early-Stage Diabetes. Journal of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Neural Network (JAIMLNN) ISSN, 2799-1172.
18. Chen, Z., Xie, M., Zu, Q., & Abdufattokhov, S. (2023). Electrical Automation Intelligent Control System Based on Internet of Things Technology. Electrica, 23(2).
19. Abdufattokhov, S., Mahamatov, N., Ibragimova, K., Gulyamova, D., & Yuldashev, D. (2022). Supervisory optimal control using machine learning for building thermal comfort. Operations Research and Decisions, 32(4).